

Weed Management in Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) under Minimum Tillage and Crop Residues

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Introduction

Different tillage system can influence the composition of weed species and changing from traditional tillage to conservation (minimum tillage) can lead to shifts in weed flora in agricultural plant communities (Ball and Miller, 1993). The shift from conventional tillage to conservation, can make control weed difficult (Andrew and Kelton, 2011). Many weed species flourish when intense tillage operations are minimized and therefore, minimum tillage has been characterized by greater weed densities than conventional tillage systems (Sosnoskie *et al.*, 2006). With a reduction in tillage, farmers lose weed control offered from seed burial and pre-sowing germination. As a result, producers wishing to adopt minimum tillage are likely to be primarily dependent upon on the extensive use of chemicals applied, such as pre-sowing, pre-emergence and post-emergence. But options for weed control must reduce selection pressure for herbicide resistance as well as provide season-long weed suppression. A cover crop or previous crop residue help in reducing weed infestation through reduced weed emergence. An on-farm experiment was conducted, to examine the performance of tillage practices and residue levels on crop and weeds.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was conducted on farm at the Vangnamari union under Gouripur upazila of Mymensingh district of Bangladesh from 28 November 2013 to 23 February 2014. Wheat cv. *BARI Gom-26*, was sown with 6 tillage and weed control practices *viz.*, **W₁**: Conventional tillage + one weeding (Control); **W₂**: Roundup (RU) + Strip tillage (ST); **W₃**: RU+ ST + Pre-emergence (PE) herbicide (Pendimethalin); **W₄**: RU+ ST + Post-emergence (PO) herbicide (Affinity 50.75 WP); **W₅**: RU+ ST + PE + PO; **W₆**: RU+ ST + weed-free, and 2 levels of crop residue *viz.*, **Cr₁**: Current (20%) residue and **Cr₂**: Increased (50%) residue. The treatments were laid out in randomized complete block design with 4 replications using unit plots of 9 m × 5 m. Weed species and plant densities were recorded randomly from 4 locations of 0.25 m² each at 21 days after sowing (DAS), 40 DAS and flowering stages. Weed dry matter assessed by harvesting biomass which was then oven dried at 70⁰C for 72 hours. The crop was harvested at maturity from 3 locations of 3 m² quadrats and grain yield was recorded. Data were subjected to ANOVA using MSTAT-C and means separated by Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

Results and Discussions

Weed infestation

The experimental plots were infested with 18 weed species belonging to 7 families, of which 15 were annuals and 3 perennials (Table 1). Of these weed species, 6 belonged to Poaceae, 5 to Solanaceae, 2 to each of Asteraceae and polygonaceae and 1 each of the remaining 3 families. The 5 most abundant weeds were *Alternanthera sessilis*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Echinochloa crusgalli*, *Cyperus rotundus* and *Eclipta alba*.

Table 1: Weed infestation in the experiment plots at the Vangnamari union under Guoripur upazila of Mymensingh district of Bangladesh in 2013 - 2014 wheat crop (*annual species, ** perennial species)

Species	Family	Density	Species	Family	Density
<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> *	Amaranthaceae	404	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> **	Poaceae	303
<i>Centipeda minima</i> **	Asteraceae	3	<i>Parapholis incurva</i> *	Poaceae	2
<i>Eclipta alba</i> *	Asteraceae	129	<i>Rumex maritimus</i> *	Polygonaceae	1
<i>Spilanthes acmella</i> *	Campanulaceae	13	<i>Polygonum coccineum</i> *	Polygonaceae	1
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> **	Cyperaceae	169	<i>Physalis minima</i> *	Solanaceae	9
<i>Echinochloa crusgalli</i> *	Poaceae	199	<i>Solanum torvum</i> *	Solanaceae	17
<i>E. colonum</i> *	Poaceae	41	<i>S. carolinense</i> *	Solanaceae	22
<i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i> *	Poaceae	85	<i>S. rostrum</i> *	Solanaceae	2
<i>Eleusine indica</i> *	Poaceae	9	<i>Nicotiana plumbaginifolia</i> *	Solanaceae	12

Effect of tillage on weed and crop

High weed density in the untreated control (W_1) has resulted in significant reduction (7%) of wheat yield (Table 2). Roundup application at pre-sowing (W_2) did significantly reduced weed density and biomass but this reduction was not high enough to increase grain yield of wheat compared to untreated weedy treatment (W_1). Although application of Roundup plus a pre-emergence with or without a post-emergence application of herbicide significantly reduced weed density and biomass, these treatments did not improve wheat yield compared to Roundup alone.

Table 2: Effect of tillage on density, dry matter and yield of wheat at the Vangnamari union under Guoripur upazila of Mymensingh district of Bangladesh

Tillage and weed control	Weed density (no. m ⁻²)			Weed dry matter (gm ⁻²)			Yield (t ha ⁻¹)
	21 DAS	40 DAS	Flowering	21 DAS	40 DAS	Flowering	
W_1 : Conventional tillage + one weeding	30 a	23 a	46 a	19 a	14 a	24 a	3.28 c
W_2 : Roundup (RU) + Strip tillage (ST)	21 b	17 b	30 b	18 a	13 a	16 b	3.33 bc
W_3 : RU+ ST + Pre-emergence (PE) herbicide	16 c	15 c	24 c	16 b	12 ab	13 c	3.39 b
W_4 : RU+ ST + Post-emergence (PO) herbicide	17 c	15 c	25 c	14 c	10 c	13 c	3.40 b
W_5 : RU+ ST + PE herbicide + PO herbicide	15 d	13 d	20 d	12 d	8 d	10 d	3.42 b
W_6 : RU+ ST + weed free	0 e	0 e	0 e	0 e	0 e	0 e	3.52 a
CV (%)	7.28	9.15	6.94	7.25	2.40	6.17	2.21
LSD _(0.05)	1.22	1.29	1.69	0.98	0.23	0.80	0.08

The highest weed density at 21 DAS (30), 40 DAS (23) and flowering (46) and dry matter 19, 14 and 24 gm⁻² on that 3 times, respectively and lowest yield (3.2 t ha⁻¹) were found in W₁ while the value for density and dry matter were nil in W₆. However, the lowest density 15, 13 and 19 m⁻² and dry matter 12, 8 and 10 gm⁻² were obtained at 21 DAS, 40 DAS and at flowering, respectively, on W₅. W₆ yielded the highest (3.52 t ha⁻¹) while the second highest (3.4 t ha⁻¹) from W₅. The second highest yield also produce from W₄ and W₃ (Table 2).

Effect of residues on weed and wheat

Figure 1 reveals that, the weed density at 50% residues was reduced by 19 to 30% compared to 20% residues suggesting that higher residues significantly reduced weed emergence. Biomass of weed at 50% residues was also significantly lower than 20% residues further suggesting that high residues not only reduced density of weeds but also reduced weed plant size. The reduction in weed density and biomass due to increased residues has increased wheat yield by about 4%.

Figure 1. Effect of residues on weed and wheat

Reference

- Andrew P and Jessica K (2011) Weed Control in Conservation Agriculture, Herbicides, Theory and Applications, Prof. Marcelo Larramendy (*Ed.*), ISBN: 978-953-307-975-2. InTech, Available: <http://www.intechopen.com/books/herbicides-theory-and-applications/weed-control-in-conservation-agriculture>
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